

USE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS TO DEVELOP STUDENTS' CREATIVITY

Askarova Dilafruz Ibrokhimovna

FarDU Social and Humanities

teacher of the department

Yuldasheva Dilshoda Tolkinovna

FarDU Social and Humanities

teacher of the department

ANNOTATION

This article talks about the development of students' creative abilities using innovative technologies in the educational process. The main purpose of this article is to develop the creative activity of students, work with sources that can provide broad and in-depth information on a wide range of topics, and on this basis, mastering the skills and techniques necessary to improve creative development. skills formation.

Key words : creativity, innovation, innovative tools, modern technologies,

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, the interest and attention to the use of interactive methods, innovative technologies, pedagogic and information technologies in the educational process to develop students' creativity using innovative technologies in the educational process is increasing day by day, one of the reasons for this is that until now, in traditional education, students were taught to acquire only theoretical knowledge, modern technologies teach them to search for the acquired knowledge by themselves, to study and analyze independently, and even to draw their own conclusions. . In this process, the teacher creates conditions for the development, formation, education and training of a person, creative improvement, and at the same time performs the functions of management and

training.

In the process of education, using innovative technologies, student-centered object becomes the object of development of students' creativity. Therefore, the place and role of modern teaching methods - interactive methods, innovative technologies in the training of qualified professionals in the higher education system is very important. Knowledge, experience and interactive methods of pedagogical technology and pedagogic skills ensure that students acquire knowledgeable, creative and professional skills.

MATERIALS AND METHODS. Innovation (in English innovation) is innovation. Innovative technologies are the introduction of changes to the pedagogical process and teacher and student activities, and in its implementation, innovative tools and interactive methods are fully utilized. Interactive methods are called collective thinking, which are methods of pedagogical influence and are part of the content of education. The uniqueness of these methods is that they are implemented only through the joint activity of the pedagogue and students. This process of pedagogical cooperation has its own characteristics, which include the following: forcing students not to be indifferent, to think independently, to create, to be creative, to develop critical thinking and to search; to ensure that students are constantly interested in learning during the educational process; to increase students' interest in knowledge independently and creatively approach each issue ; the organization of the activity of the teacher and the student in cooperation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS. In our opinion, the most basic principle of pedagogical technology is that it depends on the technologies chosen by the teacher and the student in order to achieve a guaranteed result from the specified goal, that is, every method used in the teaching process, in order to achieve a guaranteed result according to the goal. if the educational technology can organize a cooperative activity between the teacher and the student, both of them can achieve a positive result, if the students can think independently, think creatively, search , criticize and analyze in the educational process, and make their

own conclusions if they can do it, if they can evaluate themselves, the group, and the group can evaluate them, and the teacher can create opportunities and conditions for their activities, this process is the basis of the educational process. Each lesson, subject, subject has its own technology, that is, pedagogical technology in **the** educational process is an individual process, which is directed to a goal based on the student's experience, and is predetermined. It is a pedagogical procedure aimed at providing standardized and guaranteed results.

As can be seen from the above points, the implementation of the development of student creativity and the achievement of a guaranteed result depend on the cooperative activity of both the teacher and the student, the goal they set, the chosen content, method, form, tool, and technology. It is up to the teacher and the student to choose what kind of technology to achieve the target result, because the main goal of both parties is clear: to achieve creative development, in which the technology used is chosen depending on the conditions of the students' knowledge level, group character, creative development, for example, to achieve the result, it is necessary to work with a computer, maybe a film, handouts, drawings and posters, various literature, information technology will be needed, it depends on the teacher and the student. In addition, it is necessary to plan the teaching process in advance, in this process, the teacher should take into account the unique aspect of the educational subject, atmosphere and conditions, most importantly, the student's ability and ability, as well as the ability to organize collaborative creative activity . only then, the desired guaranteed result can be achieved. In short, the student must be brought to the center of creative improvement in education.

" Assessment" method . "Assessment" is derived from the English word "assessment" and means "evaluation". The assessment method is a set of tasks that provides an opportunity to comprehensively and objectively assess the level of students' knowledge, skills, and abilities . , interview, creative work, test, individual case, presentation, expert observation, role-playing and business games. This method mainly serves the following three purposes: comprehensive, objective assessment of students' knowledge, skills and qualifications; to determine the possibilities of developing students' knowledge, skills and qualifications; formation of a future plan (targeted program) that serves to develop students' knowledge, skills and abilities.

The history of the creation of this technology dates back to the 30-40s of the last century. Initially, the technology was used to select knowledgeable, enterprising, creative, skilled soldiers, as well as officers, from among the English and German soldiers who can correctly assess the existing military situations, effectively manage the process of military actions, and organize rational action in the necessary places. .

CONCLUSION. To sum up, the use of innovative technologies in activities for the formation of students' creativity will help students master the educational process better and become mature staff in the future. The development of this knowledge is carried out by pedagogues on the basis of special pedagogical methods and technologies. Students develop practical skills in the process of working directly in these methods. This, in turn, allows the pedagogue to realize his goal in the process of imparting knowledge.

REFERENCES

1. Dilshodbek o'g'li, R. S., & Boxodirjon o'g'li, V. A. (2022). XORIJ PSIXOLOGLARINING ISHLARIDA SHAXSNING TADQIQ ETILISHI. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION*, 1(12), 39-47.
2. Vosiljonov, A. (2022). LINGVISTIK TADQIQOTLARDA KORPUS O'RGANISH OBYEKTI SIFATIDA. *IJTIMOY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(11), 176-182.
3. Vosiljonov, A. (2022). Basic theoretical principles of corpus linguistics. *Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research*, 3(2), 1-3.
4. Vosiljonov, A. (2022). PRAGMALINGVISTIKA VA UNING TAHLILIIY SHAKLLANISH TARIXI. *Science and innovation*, 1(B8), 99-105.
5. Ботирова, Н. (2020). Обучающие возможности тестовых технологий. *Профессиональное образование и общество*, (3), 68-71.
6. Ботирова, Н. Д. (2019). Развитию продуктивного мышления младших школьников. *Гуманитарный трактат*, (61), 4-6.
7. Ботирова, Н. Д. Развитию продуктивного мышления младших школьников development of productive thinking of younger schoolboys. *Журнал выпускается ежемесячно, публикует статьи по гуманитарным наукам. Подробнее на*, 4.
8. Ботирова, Н. Д., & Алимджонова, М. Ю. (2022). БЎЛАЖАК

БОШЛАНҒИЧ СИНФ ЎҚИТУВЧИЛАРИНИ ЭВРИСТИК ФАОЛИЯТИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШНИНГ ТАШКИЛИЙ ОМИЛЛАРИ. Scientific progress, 3(4), 519-524.

9. Botirova Nasiba Djurabayevna INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING MATHEMATICS . Eastern European Scientific Journal Germany. 128 – 132 p. <http://www.auris-verlag.de>

10. Alimjanova, M. (2020). PEDAGOGICAL SYSTEM OF FORMATION OF RESPONSIBILITY IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS ON THE BASIS OF NATIONAL VALUES. Theoretical & Applied Science, (4), 914-917.

11. Alimjonova, M. Y. (2021). The role of the national values in the history of pedagogical education. ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal, 11(3), 1040-1044.

12. Alimjanova, M. (2021). ABOUT GENDER STEREOTYPES. Emergent: Journal of Educational Discoveries and Lifelong Learning (EJEDL), 2(06), 72-76.

13. Janabergenova, A. J. (2018). Organization and Forms of Students' Independent Work on Higher Mathematics at Pedagogical University. Eastern European Scientific Journal, (2).

14. Janabergenova, A. J. (2021). Setting Goals on Smart Techniques and Affecting Student Motivation. Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology, 9333-9336.

15. Askarova, D. (2022). FORMATION OF CREATIVITY AND BOOKREADERS QUALITIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTION. Science and innovation, 1(B8), 1039-1044.

16. Askarova, D. I. (2022). The Role Of Folk Pedagogy In The Development Of Creativity Of Students Of Higher Educational Institutions. Oriental Journal of Social Sciences, 2(02), 89-96.

17. Dilafruz, A. (2022). Maktabgacha Yoshdagi Bolalarda Va Oilada Gender Xususiyatlarni Shakllantirish Omillari. Innovation In The Modern Education System, 2(18), 183-189.

18. Askarova, D. I. (2022). USE OF INTERACTIVE METHODS IN DEVELOPING CREATIVITY OF STUDENTS OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS. *Emergent: Journal of Educational Discoveries and Lifelong Learning (EJEDL)*, 3(10), 92-97.
19. Askarova, D. I., & Jabborova, M. K. (2022). The Introduction Of Gender Issues In Preschool Education On The Example Of Folk Pedagogy. *Oriental Journal of Social Sciences*, 2(05), 81-87.
20. Jabborova, M. (2021). THE IMPORTANCE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIETY. *Экономика и социум*, (6-1), 129-132.
21. Jabborova, M. (2022). BO'LAJAK PEDAGOGLARNI TAYYORLASH TIZIMIDA MALAKAVIY AMALIYOTNING ROLI. *Scientific progress*, 3(4), 167-173.
22. Kodiraliyevna, J. M. (2022). TARBIYACHI KASBINING MA'NAVIY AXLOQIY NEGIZLARI. *Central Asian Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies (CARJIS)*, 2(Special Issue 2), 64-70.
23. Zhabborova, M. R. K. (2021). Мактабгача таълим соҳаси талабаларида бошқарувчанлик қобилиятларини ривожлантириш. *Молодой ученый*, (17), 394-395.
24. Dilafruz, Y., Marifatxon, J., Rasuljonovna, E. Z., & Muqaddasxon, M. (2022). МАКТАБГАЧА ТА'ЛИМГА YANGICHA YONDASHUV. *Central Asian Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies (CARJIS)*, 2(Special Issue 3), 121-125.
25. E. Najmiddinov, A. Rasujonov, & J. Rahimov (2022). FARG'ONA VODIYSI SUV HAVZALARIDAGI BALIQLAR GELMINTLARI. *Science and innovation*, 1 (D8), 145-151. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7335759
26. Najmiddinov, Eldor , Rasuljonov, Adhamjon, & Rahimov, Javohir (2022). FISH HELMINTHS IN FISH RESERVOIRS OF FERGANA VALLEY. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2 (10), 1049-

1054.

27. E. Najmiddinov (2022). ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА “ИХТИОЛОГИЯ ВА ГИДРОБИОЛОГИЯ” СОҲАЛАРИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ ИСТИҚБОЛЛАРИ. *Science and innovation*, 1 (D8), 152-160. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7335800
28. E. Najmiddinov (2022). TABIATNING MAKTABGACHA TA’LIM YOSHIDAGI BOLALARNI BARKAMOL AVLOD BO’LIB SHAKLLANISHIDAGI ANAMIYATI. *Science and innovation*, 1 (B8), 149-154. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7336353
29. Юлдашев, Э., & Нажмиддинов, Э. (2013). БРАКОНИДЫ (Hymenoptera, Braconidae) РОДА ROGAS NEES ФАУНЫ СРЕДНЕЙ АЗИИ. In *Биоразнообразие и рациональное использование природных ресурсов* (pp. 134-136).
30. Нажмиддинов, Э. Х., Кучбоев, А. Э., Мухаммадиев, М. А., & Соатов, Б. Б. (2021). Эколого-морфологические характеристики нематод рода *Rhabdochona*-паразитов обыкновенной маринки. *Теория и практика борьбы с паразитарными болезнями*, (22), 387-393.
31. Kuchboev, A. E., Najmidinov, E. K., Mukhamediev, M. A., Karimova, R. R., & Yildiz, K. (2021). Morphological and ecological features of some nematodes of the genus *Rhabdochona* in marinka obtained from Fergana Valley, Uzbekistan. *Journal of Parasitic Diseases*, 45(4), 1084-1089.
32. Uljaevna, U. F., & Shavkatovna, S. R. (2021). Development and education of preschool children. *Academicia: an international multidisciplinary research journal*, 11(2), 326-329.
33. Shavkatovna, S. R. N. (2021). METHODOICAL SUPPORT OF DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE ACTIVITY OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS. *Conferencea*, 74-76.

34. Shavkatovna, S. R. (2021). DEVELOPING CRITICAL THINKING IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS. *Conferencea*, 97-102.
35. Oljayevna, O., & Shavkatovna, S. (2020). The Development of Logical Thinking of Primary School Students in Mathematics. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences*, 8(2), 235-239.
36. Shavkatovna, S. R. (2021). Methodological Support for The Development of Primary School Students' Creative Activities. *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 2, 121-123.
37. Shavkatovna, S. R. (2021). Improvement of methodological pedagogical skills of developing creative activity of primary school students. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(10), 289-292.
38. Ra'noxon, S. (2022). BOSHLANG'ICH MAKTAB O'QUVCHILARIDA MATEMATIKAGA MUNOSABAT. *IJTIMOY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(11), 203-207.
39. Шарофутдинова, Р., & Абдуллаева, С. (2022). ФИКРЛАШ ҚОБИЛИЯТИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШДА МЕНТАЛ АРИФМЕТИКА. *IJTIMOY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(11), 235-239.
40. Asqarov Anvarjon Rahimjon o'g'li. (2022). MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARNING AQLIY TARAQQIYOTINING RIVOJLANISHIDA O'YIN RIVOJLANTIRUVCHI FAOLIYAT SIFATIDA. *Uzbek Scholar Journal*, 5, 207–209.
41. Askarov, A. (2022). CREATIVE THINKING IN PRESCHOOL SOCIAL PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF DEVELOPMENT. *Science and innovation*, 1(B8), 87-91.

42. To‘lqinovna, Y. D. (2022). MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARDA MATEMATIK TASAVVURLARINI SHAKLLANTIRISH METODLARI. *BOSHQARUV VA ETIKA QOIDALARI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(11), 25-31.
43. Yuldasheva Dilshoda To‘Lqinovna (2022). MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARDA BADIY TASVIRLAR ORQALI IZCHIL NUTQNI RIVOJLANTIRISH. *Science and innovation*, 1 (1), 741-750. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.653521
44. Yuldasheva, D. (2021). AGE AND THE SECOND LANGUAGE ACQUISITION. *ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions*, 2(04), 124-130.
45. Tulkinovna, Y. D. (2021). On the Principle of Simple to Complex in the Development of Speech in Young Children. *International Journal of Culture and Modernity*, 10, 32-35.
46. Ummatqulov, T. (2022). INSON SOG'LOM BO'LISHIDA VALEOLOGIYA FANINING AHAMIYATI. *Eurasian Journal of Social Sciences, Philosophy and Culture*, 2(12), 80-88.
47. SultonaliMannopov, A., AbdusalomSoliev, U., & TokhirShokirov, R. (2021). Development of Uzbek National Singing Art during Independence. *Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology*, 6845-6853.
48. Шокиров, Т. Н. (2022). МИЛЛИЙ МУСИҚА МАДАНИЯТИ ВА УНИНГ РИВОЖЛАНИШ ИСТИҚБОЛЛАРИ (фольклор, дostonчилик, мақом мисолида). *Science and innovation*, 1(C3), 31-38.
49. Shakirov, T. N. (2022). SUCCESSION IS THE MAIN PRINCIPLE OF DEVELOPMENT OF NATIONAL MUSIC CULTURE. *Oriental Journal of Social Sciences*, 2(06), 1-10.
50. Шокиров, Т. Н. (2022). АБУ НАСР ФОРОБИЙНИНГ МУСИҚА

ИЛМИГА ҚЎШГАН ҲИССАСИ. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(10-2), 353-359.

51. Nurmamatovich, S. T. (2021). Theoretical of national music culture fundamentals.

52. Qizi, G. S., & Umarova, N. R. (2021). The use of anthroponyms and pseudonyms in alisher Navoi's gazelles. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(9), 349-353.

53. Tillaboyeva, G., & Umarova, N. R. (2021). ALISHER NAVOIY ASARLARIDA BADIY TAXALLUSLARNING QO‘LLANILISHI. *Студенческий вестник*, (13-5), 70-72.

54. Tillaboyeva, G. S. Q. (2022). ALISHER NAVOIY SHE‘RIYATIDA “SHAXS” TUSHUNCHASI. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(2), 182-196.

55. Tillaboyeva, G. S. Q. (2022). TILSHUNOSLIKDA LIBOS NOMLARI. *Scientific progress*, 3(4), 506-514.

56. Mohinur, D., & Rahimjon, U. (2022). A Study Of Memory Processes And Their Development In Preschool. *Uzbek Scholar Journal*, 5, 62-65.

57. Rahim, U. (2021, May). SOCIAL FACTORS OF THE INTERDEPENDENCE OF MENTAL AND PHYSICAL ACTIVITY. In *Archive of Conferences* (Vol. 25, No. 1, pp. 6-7).

58. Usmonov, R. (2022). O‘SMIRLAR XULQIDA NAMOIYSHKORLIK G‘AYRATLILIK XUSUSIYATLARI TADQIQ ETISH METODOLOGIYASI. *Science and innovation*, 1(B8), 127-135.

59. Usmonov, R. (2022). O‘SMIRLIK DAVRI SHAXSIGA XOS ILMIY-NAZARIY YONDOSHUVLAR. *Science and innovation*, 1(B8), 120-126.

60. Raxmonovich, U. R. (2022). O'SMIRLIK DAVRIDA NAMOYISHKORLIK, G'AYRATLILIK TAJOVUZKORLIK XUSUSIYATLARINING NAMOYON BO'LISHI. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION*, 1(12), 87-97.
61. Raxmonovich, U. R. (2022). O'SMIRLIK DAVRIDA NAMOYISHKORLIK, G'AYRATLILIK TAJOVUZKORLIK XUSUSIYATLARINING NAMOYON BO'LISHI. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION*, 1(12), 87-97.
62. Rakhmonovich, U. R. (2022). CHARACTERISTICS OF DEMONSTRATIVENESS, ENTHUSIASM AND AGGRESSIVENESS IN ADOLESCENCE. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(12), 820-824.
63. Qurbonova, S. (2022). KICHIK MAKTAB YOSHIDAGI BOLALARDA AQLIY INTELLEKTNING RIVOJLANISHI. *Eurasian Journal of Social Sciences, Philosophy and Culture*, 2(12), 73-79.
64. Қурбонова, С. (2022). ПСИХОЛОГИЯНИ ЎҚИТИШГА ЗАМОНАВИЙ ПЕДАГОГИК ТЕХНОЛОГИЯЛАРНИ ТАТБИҚ ЭТИШ. *MODELS AND METHODS FOR INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF INNOVATIVE RESEARCH*, 2(17), 191-194.
65. Qurbonova, S. (2022, June). ON THE ANALYSIS OF LEXICAL UNITS IN PSYCHOLINGUISTICS. In *International Conference on Research Identity, Value and Ethics* (pp. 512-513).
66. Miralimjanovna, Q. S. (2022). O 'SMIRLIK DAVRIDA TURLI XIL

QATLAMGA EGA BOLGANLARNING PSIXOLOGIK
XUSUSIYATLARI. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 30, 39-44.

67. Miralimjanovna, Q. S. (2022). CHET EL OLIMLARI TOMONIDAN GURUHDAGI O ‘SMIRLAR VA AUTSAYDERLAR MUAMMOSINI O ‘RGANILISHNING OZIGA XOSLIGI. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 30, 33-38.
68. Noxida, D., & Saida, Q. (2022). TALABA QIZLARNI OILAVIY HAYOTGA TAYYORLASHNING ETNOPSIXOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(11), 309-314.
69. Dilshodbek O'g'li, R. S. (2022). The Role Of Physical Culture In Providing The Psychological Health Of The Athlete. *Innovative Developments And Research In Education, Canada*.
70. Dilshodbek o'g'li, R. S. (2022). TALABALARDA TOLERANTLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISH–IJTIMOIY PSIXOLOGIK MUAMMO SIFATIDA. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 30, 66-70.
71. Dilshodbek o'g'li, R. S. (2022). PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF THE SPORTSMAN PERSONALITY DURING COMPETITIONS. *IJTIMOYIY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(11), 215-221.
72. Dilshodbek o'g'li, R. S. (2022). Motiv Va Motivatsiya Muammosining Jahon Va Mahalliy Psixologlar Tomonidan Tadqiq Etilganligi. *American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research*, 3(11), 256-259.